

RADIO FREQUENCY PLASMA IN CF₄ AS A FAST AND EFFICIENT TOOL FOR OBTAINING AND RETAINING A LONG-TERM HYDROPHOBICITY OF CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS-REINFORCED CHITOSAN FILMS

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Abstract: *Chitosan presents a great matrix for the alternative to conventional plastic-based packaging. In this study, chitosan-based films with cellulose nanocrystals as reinforcement were prepared and processed by the means of CF₄ plasma for various durations (from 1 to 30 s) and the change in the contact angle was observed. It increased from initial 90 ° to 100 ° already in the first second, and reached maximum at 120 ° after treatment time of 5 s. With further treatment, the water contact angle decreased slightly, possibly due to the surface etching. With X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy, it was confirmed that total fluorine concentration on the biopolymer surface reached 48 at%. Furthermore, occurrence of various C-F bonds were confirmed in performed surface analysis where CF₂-CF₂ and CF-CF₂ are being prevalent after longer treatment times. With plasma treatment, water-related properties were improved without negatively influencing the material's mechanical properties. It was observed, that the fluorine concentration, hydrophobic character and water barrier properties did not decline during the tested period of 31 days.*

Keywords: biopolymers, hydrophobic surface modification, packaging, plasma processing, chitosan

1 INTRODUCTION

Chitosan, a derivate of chitin, the second most abundant biopolymer in nature, has been extensively studied for numerous applications. Because of its ability to form films, it presents a suitable matrix for sustainable packaging such as wrappings, bags and sachet. Such films are non-toxic, biodegradable, have good mechanical, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Various additives, such as natural extracts and etheric oils, can be incorporated in order to enhance antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Bajić et al., 2019b). It was previously discovered that the addition of cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) into chitosan film forming solution enhance mechanical properties with improvement of the film's strength for 120 % (Lavrič et al., 2021). However, water-related properties, such as water repellence and prevention of water vapour transmission are not as good as in conventional, petroleum-based packaging. Hydrophobicity can be improved by two approaches: i) modification of the surface chemistry with non-polar agents and/or ii) changing the morphology by roughening the surface. So far, reports on hydrophobization of chitosan films include synthesis functionalization of chitosan surface with various reagents resulting in N-lauryl chitosan, N-dimethylaminopropyl chitosan (Muzzarelli et al., 2000), chitosan methylcarbamate and ethylcarbamate (Cárdenas et al., 2002) or addition of hydrophobic additives such as Carnuba wax (Despond et al., 2005). Plasma processing is ultrafast and efficient in hydrophobization of the materials, but is not yet well researched. Furthermore, no harmful chemicals are needed and no liquid waste is produced.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Film preparation and plasma processing

Chitosan films reinforced with CNCs were prepared according to a previously described protocol (Bajić et al., 2019a). Briefly, chitosan was dissolved in aqueous solution of lactic acid (1 v/v %) in amount of 1 wt%. Glycerol was added for its plasticizing effects in amount of 30 wt% according to the mass of biopolymer. CNCs were added in amount to reach 3 wt% according to the mass of biopolymer. The films were then dried in the ventilation oven (ventilation rate 30 %) for 48 h. The obtained samples were light-brown and transparent. The sample in size of approximately 2x6 cm was placed on the microscopic glass and fixed with double-sided carbon tape on the bottom side introduced into the plasma system schematically presented in Figure 1. The setup is described in more detail in Holc et al. (2018). In the present study, the

treatments were carried out with CF_4 as a carrier gas, power of 150 W, at pressure of 50 Pa for 1 s, 2 s, 3 s, 5 s, 10 s, 20 s and 30 s.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of plasma processing system.

2. 2 Surface analysis

Hydrophilic to hydrophobic conversion was followed through static water contact angle (WCA) measurement immediately after the treatment. The samples were analysed as they were treated, on the glass substrate with sessile drop method, using goniometer Drop Shape Analyser DSA-100 (Krüss GmbH, Hamburg, Germany). The angle was calculated from an image captured 5 s after a drop of MilliQ water with volume of $4 \mu\text{L}$ was released onto the surface. 4 replicates were taken for each sample. To further inspect the modification and surface saturation, the surface chemical composition of the samples was analysed by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS instrument TFA XPS from Physical Electronics, Munich, Germany). The samples were excited with monochromatic $\text{Al K}\alpha_{1,2}$ radiation at 1486.6 eV over an area of $400 \mu\text{m}^2$. Photoelectrons were detected with a hemispherical analyzer positioned at an angle of 45° with respect to the normal of the sample surface. XPS survey spectra were measured at a pass energy of 187 eV using an energy step of 0.4 eV. High-resolution XPS spectra of carbon C1s were measured at a pass energy of 29.35 eV using an energy step of 0.125 eV. An additional electron source was used for surface charge neutralization. The C-C component in C1s was set to the binding energy of 284.8 eV. The measured spectra were analysed using MultiPak v8.1c software (supplied by Physical Electronics, Munich, Germany). The C1s spectra were fitted with the Gauss-Lorentzian function. The width and positions of the peaks were fixed during the fitting procedure.

2. 3 Moisture Content, Thickness and Mechanical Properties

Moisture content (MC) was analysed with HE53 Moisture Analyzer (Mettler Toledo, United States). The thickness of the films was measured with ABS Digital Thickness Gauge (Mitutoyo, Aurora, USA). Tensile strength and

elongation at break were measured according to guidelines of the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) D 882 standard method (ASTM C1147-D359) with XLW Auto Tensile Tester (Labthink, China).

3 RESULTS

It was observed that the WCA increased rapidly in the first two seconds of the processing, rising from $92^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ to $119^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$, and settled around 120° , which points to saturation of surface with fluorine. The stability of the modification was confirmed through ageing of the sample treated with plasma for 5 s. The WCA remained constant during the period of 31 days (Figure 2a). Considering the atomic composition of the treated samples presented in Figure 2b, it is evident that the saturation of surface with fluorine occurs concurrently with the WCA maximum, after 3 s of treatment, with the atomic concentration 48 at%. For further analysis, the sample treated for 5 s was employed. In Figure 2c and d, high resolution C 1s deconvoluted spectra of the untreated and treated samples are presented. The observed peaks placed at 289 eV, 288.2 eV, 286.8 eV and 284.3 eV correspond to O-C=O, O-C-O, C-O and C-C bonds, respectively. Their intensity decreases after plasma treatment. At the same time, the newly formed bonds related to fluorine appeared. The most prominent are $\text{CF}_2\text{-CF}_2$ and CF-CF_2 , followed by CF_3 and O-CF_2 and O-CF_3 . The peak formerly corresponding only to O-C-O overlaps with CF-CF_2 after the treatment. The analysis was repeated after 31 days and confirmed the constant composition.

Regarding the MC, it was observed that in the treated film it was $9.2 \pm 0.32\%$, which is lower than its untreated counterpart where the measured MC was $11.6 \pm 0.42\%$ (Figure 3). The thickness of the films did not vary between treated (0.10 ± 0.011 mm) and not treated films (0.10 ± 0.021 mm). The treatment did not negatively impact mechanical properties of the films, on the contrary, tensile strength (TS) and elongation at break (ϵ) both increased. TS with initial value of 1.4 ± 0.4 MPa was increased to 2.3 ± 0.5 MPa, while ϵ increased from $63 \pm 13\%$ to $78 \pm 10\%$.

Figure 2: a) Time-evolution of the water contact angle and ageing of the sample treated for 5 s, b) atomic composition of the films in dependence to treatment time c) high-resolution C 1s spectra of the not-treated sample and d) high-resolution C 1s spectra of the sample treated for 5 s.

Figure 3: Tensile strength and moisture content of the non-treated and treated sample.

4 CONCLUSION

In this research, chitosan-based films with incorporated cellulose nanocrystals were processed with CF₄ plasma. Fluorine, bonding to the surface mainly through CF₂-CF₂ and CF-CF₂ bonds, provided the increase in the films' water resistance, without negatively affecting their mechanical properties. The

composition of the films and obtained higher hydrophobicity remained stable over the period of 31 days.

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